

13th International Seminar on
Differential Equations, Dynamical Systems
and Applications

Department of Mathematical Sciences
Isfahan University of Technology
July 13 to July 15, 2016

A Numerical Approach for the Approximate Solution of Fractional Pantograph Differential Equations

Parisa Rahimkhani^{*}, Yadollah Ordokhani

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University,
Tehran, Iran

Abstract

In this paper, a new numerical method for solving fractional pantograph differential equations is presented. The method is based upon fractional-order Taylor multi-scaling function approximations. First, the fractional-order Taylor multi-scaling function is presented. An operational matrix of fractional order integration is derived and is utilized to reduce the under study problem to system of algebraic equations.

Keywords: Fractional pantograph differential equations, Collocation method, fractional-Taylor method, Caputo derivative, Operational matrix.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2010): 34A08, 34K28, 65L60.

1 Introduction

Delay differential equations (DDE) have various applications in mathematical modeling, for example, physiological and pharmaceutical kinetics, chemical kinetics, the navigational control of ships and aircrafts, population dynamics, and infectious diseases. They arise when the rate of change of a time-dependent process in its mathematical modeling is not only determined by its present state but also by a certain past state. The pantograph equation is one of the most important kinds of DDEs, and plays an important role in explaining many different phenomena. The delay pantograph differential equations arise in many applications such as electro-dynamic. The Doughty spring Pantograph has been designed to be lightweight and compact, with strength, safety and ease of use being the main features. Loads from 5 to 36 kg can be suspended from overhead tracks or barrels and quickly positioned with height ranges of 2.2-5 m. A studio pantograph is shown in Fig. 1, which is taken from (5).

2 Preliminaries and notation

In this section we present some basic definitions needed in the following parts of the paper.

^{*}Speaker: P.rahimkhani@alzahra.ac.ir

Figure 1: A -shaped pantograph for electrical pickup.

2.1 The fractional derivative and integral

There are various definitions of fractional derivative and integration. The widely used definition of a fractional derivative is the Caputo definition, and a fractional integration is the Riemann-Liouville definition.

Definition 2.1. *The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\nu \geq 0$ is defined as (2)*

$$I^\nu f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-\nu}} ds, & \nu > 0, t > 0, \\ f(t), & \nu = 0. \end{cases}$$

For the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral we have (2)

$$I^\nu t^\beta = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta+\nu+1)} t^{\nu+\beta}, \quad \beta > -1.$$

Definition 2.2. *Caputo's fractional derivative of order ν is defined as (2)*

$$D^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{\nu+1-n}} ds, \quad n-1 < \nu \leq n, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For the Caputo derivative we have (2)

$$D^\nu I^\nu f(t) = f(t), \quad I^\nu D^\nu f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

2.2 Fractional-order Taylor vector

The fractional-order Taylor vector is defined as (1)

$$T_m^{(\gamma)}(t) = [1, t^\gamma, t^{2\gamma}, \dots, t^{m\gamma}], \quad (1)$$

where m is a positive integer and $\gamma > 0$, is a real number.

3 A new family of functions

We construct a new family of functions on the interval $[0, 1]$, as

$$\phi_{n,m}^{(\gamma)}(t) = \begin{cases} t^{m\gamma}, & \frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}} \leq t \leq \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1, n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$,

We let

$$\Psi^{(\gamma)}(t) = [\phi_{1,0}^{(\gamma)}(t), \phi_{1,1}^{(\gamma)}(t), \dots, \phi_{1,M-1}^{(\gamma)}(t) | \dots | \phi_{2^{k-1},0}^{(\gamma)}(t), \phi_{2^{k-1},1}^{(\gamma)}(t), \dots, \phi_{2^{k-1},M-1}^{(\gamma)}(t)]^T. \quad (3)$$

4 Operational matrix of the fractional integration

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integration of the vector $\Psi^{(\gamma)}(t)$ given in Eq. (3) can be expressed by

$$I^{(\alpha)}\Psi^{(\gamma)}(t) = F(t, \alpha)\Psi^{(\gamma)}(t). \quad (4)$$

where $F^{(\alpha)}$ is the $\hat{m} \times \hat{m}$ ($\hat{m} = 2^{k-1}M$) operational matrix of fractional integration of order α .

Using Eqs. (1), (2) and the properties of the operator I^α we have

$$\begin{aligned} I^\alpha T_m^{(\gamma)}(t) &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha, \frac{\Gamma(\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(\gamma+\alpha+1)} t^{\gamma+\alpha}, \frac{\Gamma(2\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(2\gamma+\alpha+1)} t^{2\gamma+\alpha}, \dots, \frac{\Gamma(m\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(m\gamma+\alpha+1)} t^{m\gamma+\alpha} \right]^T \\ &= t^\alpha G^{(\alpha)} T_m^{(\gamma)}(t) = H(t, \alpha) T_m^{(\gamma)}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where

$$G^{(\alpha)} = \text{diag} \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}, \frac{\Gamma(\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(\gamma+\alpha+1)}, \frac{\Gamma(2\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(2\gamma+\alpha+1)}, \dots, \frac{\Gamma(m\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(m\gamma+\alpha+1)} \right].$$

Therefore, the operational matrix of fractional integration of fractional-order Taylor multi-scaling functions as

$$F(t, \alpha) = \text{diag}[H(t, \alpha), H(t, \alpha), \dots, H(t, \alpha)]. \quad (6)$$

5 Numerical method

In this paper, we consider the fractional pantograph differential equation

$$D^\alpha y(t) = f(t, y(t), y(q_1 t), y(q_2 t) \dots, y(q_l t), D^{\alpha_1} y(q_1 t), D^{\alpha_2} y(q_2 t), \dots, D^{\alpha_l} y(q_l t)), \quad (7)$$

subject to the initial conditions

$$y^{(i)}(0) = \mu_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m-1. \quad (8)$$

Here, $m-1 < \alpha \leq m, 0 < q_r < 1, 0 \leq \alpha_r < \alpha \leq m$; l is a real constant, y is an unknown function and f is a continuous linear or nonlinear function.

We expand $D^\alpha y(t)$ by new functions as

$$D^\alpha y(t) \simeq C^T \Psi^{(\gamma)}(t), \quad (9)$$

By using Eqs. (4) and (9), for $r = 1, 2, \dots, l$ we have

$$y(t) \simeq C^T F(t, \alpha) \Psi^{(\gamma)}(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \frac{\mu_i}{i!} t^i, \quad y(q_r t) \simeq C^T F(q_r t, \alpha) \Psi^{(\gamma)}(q_r t) + \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \frac{\mu_i q_r^i}{i!} t^i, \quad (10)$$

Also, from Eq. (10), for $r = 1, 2, \dots, l$ we get

$$D^{\alpha_r} y(t) \simeq C^T F(t, \alpha - \alpha_r) \Psi^{(\gamma)}(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \frac{\mu_i}{i!} D^{\alpha_r} (t^i), \quad (11)$$

$$D^{\alpha_r} y(q_r t) \simeq C^T F(q_r t, \alpha - \alpha_r) \Psi^{(\gamma)}(q_r t) + \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \frac{\mu_i q_r^i}{i!} D^{\alpha_r} (t^i), \quad (12)$$

Here, by substituting Eqs. (9)-(12) in Eq. (7), we obtain an algebraic equation with \hat{m} unknowns. Next, we collocate this equation at the \hat{m} zeros of shifted Legendre polynomials $P_{\hat{m}}(t)$. These equations give \hat{m} nonlinear algebraic equations, which can be solved for the unknown vector C using Newton's iterative method.

5.1 Numerical examples

Example 5.1. Consider the following fractional nonlinear delay differential equations (3)

$$D^\alpha y(t) = 1 - 2y^2\left(\frac{t}{2}\right), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1. \quad (13)$$

The exact solution, when $\alpha = 1$ is $y(t) = \sin(t)$. In Table 1, by choosing $k = 2, M = 9, 13$ and $\gamma = \alpha$ we compare our results with Modified Chebyshev wavelet method (3). Figure 1 shows approximate curve for some different values of α with $k = 2, M = 9, \gamma = \alpha$ and the exact solution.

Table 1: Comparison of absolute error of $y(t)$ for Example 4.1.

t	Ref.(3)	Our method	
		$M = 9$	$M = 13$
0	1.23×10^{-22}	0	0
0.125	1.71×10^{-12}	5.91×10^{-11}	0
0.250	2.47×10^{-12}	7.56×10^{-9}	0
0.375	9.36×10^{-12}	1.29×10^{-7}	0
0.500	1.79×10^{-11}	9.64×10^{-7}	7.22×10^{-16}
0.625	1.89×10^{-11}	4.59×10^{-6}	1.92×10^{-14}
0.750	3.04×10^{-12}	1.64×10^{-5}	2.98×10^{-13}
0.875	1.64×10^{-12}	4.79×10^{-5}	3.01×10^{-12}
1	4.51×10^{-10}	1.24×10^{-11}	1.39×10^{-17}

Figure 2: Solutions by the proposed method at different $\alpha, M = 9, k = 2, \gamma = \alpha$ and the exact solution for Example 4.1.

Example 5.2. Consider the fractional nonlinear neutral delay differential equation (4)

$$D^\alpha y(t) = \frac{1}{2}y(t) + \frac{1}{2}y\left(\frac{t}{2}\right)D^\alpha y\left(\frac{t}{2}\right), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1. \quad (14)$$

The exact solution, when $\alpha = 1$ is $y(t) = e^t$. In Table 2, by choosing $k = 2, M = 10, 13$ and $\gamma = \alpha$ we compare our results with the method of (4). Fig.2 shows that proposed solution converges to the exact solution when α approaches 1.

Table 2: Comparison of absolute error of $y(t)$ for Example 4.2.

t	Ref.(4)	Our method	
		$M = 10$	$M = 13$
0	0	0	0
0.1	5.38×10^{-12}	2.22×10^{-16}	0
0.2	1.15×10^{-11}	2.22×10^{-16}	2.22×10^{-16}
0.3	2.14×10^{-11}	1.33×10^{-15}	0
0.4	6.30×10^{-12}	4.51×10^{-14}	2.22×10^{-16}
0.5	3.08×10^{-11}	6.61×10^{-13}	6.66×10^{-16}
0.6	1.57×10^{-11}	5.92×10^{-12}	7.55×10^{-15}
0.7	4.32×10^{-11}	3.78×10^{-11}	7.73×10^{-14}
0.8	6.08×10^{-11}	1.88×10^{-10}	5.77×10^{-13}
0.9	6.72×10^{-11}	7.77×10^{-10}	3.39×10^{-12}
1	8.36×10^{-10}	2.22×10^{-16}	0

Figure 3: Solutions by the proposed method at different α , $M = 10$, $k = 2$, $\gamma = \alpha$ and exact solution for Example 4.2.

References

- [1] Krishnasamy V.S., and Razzaghi M. (2015), *The numerical solution of the BagleyTorvik equation with fractional Taylor method*, J. Comput. Nonlinear Dynam. 11(15) (6 pages) doi: 10.1115/1.4032390.
- [2] Rahimkhani P., Ordokhani Y., and Babolian E. (2016), *Fractional-order Bernoulli wavelets and their applications*, Appl. Math. Model. doi: 10.1016/j.apm.2016.04.026.
- [3] Saeed U., ur Rehman M., and Iqbal M.A. (2015), *Modified Chebyshev wavelet methods for fractional delay-type equations*, Appl. Math. Comput. 264 431–442.
- [4] Saeed U., and ur Rehman M. (2014), *Hermite wavelet method for fractional delay differential equations*, Journal of Difference Equations, 2014 1–8.
- [5] Sedaghat S., Ordokhani Y., and Dehghan M. (2012), *Numerical solution of the delay differential equations of pantograph type via Chebyshev polynomials*, Commun. Nonl. Sci. Numer. Simulat. 17 4815–4830